

Designing a Multi-Epitope Vaccine against Human Cytomegalovirus: an Immunoinformatics Approach

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Abstract

"Cytomegalovirus (CMV) is identified as the most frequent inborn viral contagion in people and an important matter of morbidity and destruction in immunocompromised owners". Cytomegalovirus is a typical herpes virus. Also distinguished as HCMV or human herpesvirus 5 (HHV-5). Once tainted, the human body holds the virus for life. CMV settles from person to person over body liquids, like blood, saliva, urine, semen and breast milk. "The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention organization" (CDC) predicted that around 50% of grown-ups in the United States have incurred the virus by forty years old. It afflicts men and women fairly, at any life and notwithstanding of ethnicity.

Fever, wetness, tiredness, restlessness, sore throat, enlarged glands, muscle strain, low desire and loss of weight are the obvious indications. But recurring and fundamental CMV have more dangerous symptoms and critical conditions like as jaundice, fever, pneumonia, cold, spots under the surface body, Purple color surface stains, a blemish, or all, developed liver, kidney, large spleen, low birth weight, breakdowns etc. Notwithstanding these debilitating maladies, no prescription to prevent them improvement or treatment is open till now.

That's why we proposed to express a multi-epitope vaccine upon CMV by employing an Immuno bioinformatics road. For this desire, we practised the Human CMV spike protein to ascertain the dominant. After study of the specification of these epitopes we selected only six epitopes to create the desire vaccine against the human Cytomegalovirus. All features of a perfect vaccine was present of our designed vaccine such as non-toxin, non-allergenic and highly soluble etc.

Moreover, our created vaccine showed the excellent score in all physiochemical and in lifetime in the host cell.

Keywords: HCMV; Multiepitope vaccine; Immunoinformatics; Dynamic simulation

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Introduction

Cytomegalovirus (CMV) is in the subfamily Betaherpesviridae, in the family Herpesviridae, in the order Herpesvirales, in a genus of viruses [1]. Humans toil as common hosts. Total 8 species in this genus in sample species, Human betaherpesvirus 5 that affect people. Complications linked with HCMV-5 hold pneumonia [2,3]. Infrequent species of Cytomegalovirus recognised and selected for several vertebrates [4]. The most inquired is human affected cytomegalovirus, which is also recognised as a human (HHV-5) [5]. jaundice, fever, pneumonia, points under the body skin, Purple colour skin splotches, a rash on the body, or both, the enlarged liver in body, the enlarged spleen on the body, coarse birth weight of baby, fits and persistent hearing loss are the common consequences of CMV disease [6-8]. Like the other gut microbiota,

this HCMB play an important role to create disease [7]. A huge number of CMV end-organ complications territory on human health. Pneumonia ("Cytomegalovirus pneumonia disease" is marked by the symptoms of the pulmonary infection along with the CMV in lavage liquor or lung cell specimens), Gastrointestinal disorder [9] ("Cytomegalo gastrointestinal disorder" is characterised by identity of an aggregate of medical indications from the gastrointestinal area, conclusions of macroscopic wounds area endoscopy, and showing of cytomegalovirus infection in the specimen), Hepatitis ("Cytomegalo hepatitis" is characterised by the findings raised bilirubin and/or enzyme levels during liver testing, the need of any other documented that cause for hepatitis and exposure of Cytomegalovirus germs in a liver cell biopsy sample) [10], CNS disorder ("CNS syndrome" is defined by the description of CNS indications together this the

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disclosure of CMV in the sample, by production or PCR, or in brain units, by histopathologic trial, immunochemical examination, or in vitro hybridization), Retinitis (Lesions typical of of cytomegalic retinitis settled by an expert.), Cytomegalo nephritis and Cytomegalo cystitis are another which associated with CMV[11], Cystitis (“Cytomegalovirus cystitis” is exposed by the exposure of cytomegalovirus infection (by culture, in vitro hybridization) concurrently with a classification of cytomegalovirus infection, Pancreatitis is also associated with this viral infection [9]. Moreover, by these infections, cytomegalovirus is associated statistically, stimulated by bacterial superinfection, that is known as “indirect effects” of cytomegalovirus [12]. Some research showed that cytomegalovirus is associated with sensitivity [13,14], lungs organ [15], kidney organ [16-18], and innard [17] transplantings. Cytomegalovirus is responsible for Bone marrow operations [19] and liver operations [20]. For sensitive heart patient, preventive ganciclovir use lessen the fungal disease [21]. A huge randomized, placebo-controlled trial which included kidney operation patients revealed that it can decrease non-herpesvirus diseases [22]. Although disease with cytomegalovirus is usually symptomless, there is somebody at risk for cytomegalovirus disorder. There already attempts made for thirty years to produce vaccines for cytomegalovirus infections. However, in spite of these attempts, no vaccine got licensure [23]. Unfortunately, this infectious is also associated with the birth-giving child from

mother [24]. Therefore, we decided a glycoprotein which has the highest antigenic average among 75 HCMV glycoproteins. Then we prophesied CTL, HTL and MHC Class-2 epitopes for forming the HCMV vaccine. After prophesied we performed Peptide modelling and molecular docking, Sketching and developing of multi-epitope vaccine, Physicochemical and immunological evaluation, Secondary structure prediction, homology modelling, 3D structure clarification and validation, docking investigations, Molecular simulation, Immune response simulation and Codon based adaptation and in silico cloning steps to the formate final vaccine. A flow chart outlining the overall procedure in **Figure 1**.

Materials and Methods

Proteome retrieval and antigen collection

“For the purpose of antigen choice, we choose possible HCMV proteomes from the (<https://www.viprbrc.org/>) database” [28]. “The surface membrane of the HCMV is set by the spike proteins. With the cooperation of these proteins, they attach with the human host and penetrate their genome” [29]. “For the literal relationship of glycoproteins in pathogenesis, so we weighed the spike protein of the HCMV for multiepitope vaccine plan”. “Firstly, the chosen protein sequences of the cytomegalovirus had downloaded in the FASTA format file”. “The shielding antigens of the surface coprotein were checked by ([```

graph TD
 PR\[Proteome Retrieval\] --> AS\[Antigen Selection\]
 AS --> EP\[Epitope Prediction\]
 EP --> TCE\[T-Cell Epitopes\]
 EP --> BCE\[B-Cell Epitopes\]
 TCE --> EE\[Epitope Evaluation\]
 BCE --> EE
 EE --> MD\[Molecular Docking\]
 EE --> ES\(\(Epitope Selection\)\)
 ES --> VAC\(\(Vaccine Construct\)\)
 MD --> VAC
 AD\[Adjuvant\] --> VAC
 LI\[Linker\] --> VAC
 VAC --> SS\[Secondary Structure\]
 VAC --> TS\[Tertiary Structure\]
 TS --> SV\[Structural Validation\]
 TS --> MD2\[Molecular Docking\]
 TS --> DS\[Dynamics\]
 TS --> SIM\[Simulation\]
 VAC --> PC\[Physicochemistry\]
 VAC --> IS\[Immune Simulation\]
 VAC --> ISC\[In silico Cloning\]

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**Figure 1** Schematic depiction of our workflow procedure.

ddg-pharmfac.net/vaxijen/) database [30] with a threshold value of 0.4 was set for it [31]. Conclusively, we chose the spike protein with the most powerful antigenic score for additional investigations”.

### Forecast and evaluation of cytotoxic T-lymphocyte epitopes

“Cytotoxic T-lymphocytes (CTLs) have the ability to kill other contagious cells efficiently with the direct process [32]. We use the NetCTL v1.2 server available at <http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/services/NetCTL/> [33]. The prophesied epitopes were more valued within the VaxiJen v2.0 [34], ToxinPred (<http://crdd.osdd.net/raghava/toxinpred/>) [35], and AllerTop v2.0 (<https://ddg-pharmfac.net/AllerTOP/>) [36] servers. The default parameters of those servers were done for all the prophecies”.

### Forecast and evaluation of helper T-lymphocyte epitopes

“Helper T-cells (HTLs) are an essential part of adaptive resistance that sees different antigens and begins B and cytotoxic T-cells ending in the loss of the dangerous pathogen. To learn the HTL epitopes, we did the IEDB’s MHC class II necessary allele forecast tool, free at <http://tools.iedb.org/mhcii/>. The HTL epitopes were chosen based on a percentile level of 5% doing the Agreement method [37]. The prophesied epitopes were more assessed based on antigenicity exerting vaxijen server v2.0 (<http://www.ddg-pharmfac.net/vaxijen/>) [30]”.

### Forecast and evaluation of linear Blymphocyteepitopes

“B-cell epitopes are required to influence humoral or antibody-mediated safety [38]. Therefore, we used the iBCE-EL server, free at <http://www.thegleelab.org/iBCE-EL/> with default levels”[39].

### Modelling of multi-epitope vaccine

“The vaccine construct was created by applying the chosen CTL epitope, HTL epitope, and LBL epitopes as well as a perfect adjuvant that was joined by the appropriate linkers [38,40]. Here, for recognized by viral glycoproteins we used TLR4 agonist as an adjuvant [41,42]. Therefore, 50S ribosomal protein (NCBI ID: P9WHE3) was recognised as the adjuvant to enhance the immunogenicity of the vaccine applicant. The adjuvant was linked with linker EAAAK. In contrast, the elected CTL was linked with (AAY) linkers, the HTL was associated with (GPGPG) linkers also the LBL was connected with (KK) linker [38,40]. The AAY linker was used to influence protein balance, decrease more limited immunogenicity and improve epitope offering”[43,44].

### Physicochemical and immunological evaluation

“The physicochemical characteristics of the vaccine were predicted by applying the ProtParam database free at <https://web.expasy.org/protparam/> to know the functional characteristics of the vaccine [45]. We further assessed the immunological attributes within VaxiJen v2.0 [34], MHC-I immunogenicity [33], AllerTop [36], Biosoland SOLpro (<https://protein-sol.manchester.ac.uk/>) [31] website”.

**Secondary construction forecast:** “The two-dimensional basic peculiarities such as alpha-helix and random coils of the construct were recognised by SOPMA server at [https://npsa-prabi.ibcp.fr/NPSA/npsa\\_seccons.html](https://npsa-prabi.ibcp.fr/NPSA/npsa_seccons.html) [46] and PSIPRED v4.0 server at <http://bioinf.cs.ucl.ac.uk/psipred/> [47] with default value. SOPMA has more than eighty per cent prophecy correctness [46]. The 2D fundamental specialities were recovered and decided to agree with the construction nature of the vaccine”.

**Homology modelling, 3D construction clarification and validation:** “The created vaccine was offered into Galaxyweb online network portal (<http://galaxy.seoklab.org/cgi-bin/submit.cgi?type=TBM>) for (3D) structure prophecy [48]. The recognised 3D building was presented into the Galaxy Refine (<http://galaxy.seoklab.org/refine>) online web-based site for the breeding of the vaccine composition [49]. The Galaxy Refine site presents an overall full point average. The elegant building was downloaded, and the chosen structure was named depending on the effectiveness number of the quietest and highest RMSD rate. The elegant and distinguished formation was conceived practising the PyMOL v2.3.4 software [50]. The Ramachandran plot and Z-point signified was examined by the ProSA-web (<https://prosa.services.came.sbg.ac.at/prosa.php>) accessory and Procheck (<https://servicesn.mbi.ucla.edu/PROCHECK/>)” [51].

**Molecular docking investigations:** It exposes the necessary communications between modelled protein and receptor units. For this commission, we resigned the elegant vaccine model as ligand and TLR4 protein as a receptor molecule into the ClusPro v2.0 site(<https://cluspro.bu.edu/>), for docking study [52]. The TLR4 receptor (PDB ID: 3W3M) was chosen and took from the PDB site[53].

**Dynamics simulation study:** For molecular dynamics simulation, we took server-based instruments to estimate the dynamics and security of the vaccine–receptor fear critically. The obsession was resigned to the iMODS site, open at <http://imods.chaconlab.org/> [54].

**Protected rejoinder simulation:** To assess the pleasant safe reply of the vaccine, the good construct was resigned on C-IMMSIM v10.1 site free at <http://150.146.2.1/C-IMMSIM/> and the created replies were recovered for accurate pronouncement [55]. We admitted the smallest interlude point of 30 days between two applications, as reported hardy [56].

### Codon adaptation and in silico cloning Technique

Concerning the appearance of an alien gene in an organism, codon optimization more needed according to the special organism [57]. So, the construct was resigned on JCat server (<http://jcat.de/>) as the codon change. The modified course was assessed based on the codon adaptation ratio (CAI) preference and guanine-cytosine content [57]. The body in silico cloning plan was accomplished in SnapGene v4.2 [58].

## Results

### Best antigenic protein selection

“We got 75 S-proteins from India region. By antigenicity, we designed a protein with an antigenic point of 0.5350 (Vaxijen) the GenBank id was D7PI78”.

### Possible CTL epitopes

“Amidst the 115 epitopes we took the top five CTL epitopes for the main vaccine building based on the antigenicity value (Table 1)”.

### Possible HTL epitopes

“Total of 219 HTL epitopes, each was selected originally practising the IEDB site. We thought the highest fiver HTL epitopes for combining into the last vaccine assemble based on antigenicity (Table 2)”.

### Possible LBL epitopes

“Amidst all direct B cell epitopes we decided two epitopes those are antigenic, nonallergen and Grand average of hydropathicity point are negative (Table 3)”.

### Vaccine construct and fundamental premises

The vaccine was formulated using the chosen 6 epitopes based on antigenicity, allergenicity and toxicity belonging to three separate groups (2 CTL, 2HTL, and 2 LBL). The last vaccine Formed was 316 amino acids long (Figure 1).

### Physicochemical characteristics and immunological assessment

The physicochemical characteristics of the vaccine built were evaluated as given in Table 4. The molecular weight of it 28111.58 Da. Other features such as (pI) were 6.19, Number of amino acids:

**Table 1** The decided CTL epitopes for final vaccine building.

| CTL | Epitope   | C. Score | Antigenicity | Allergenicity | Toxicity  |
|-----|-----------|----------|--------------|---------------|-----------|
|     | KAHCTSHMY | 1.2081   | 0.6249       | NON-ALLERGEN  | Non-Toxin |
|     | STSVSTTKL | 0.8355   | 0.7135       | ALLERGEN      | Non-Toxin |
|     | WTMLNALIL | 0.7654   | 0.3918 NON   | NON-ALLERGEN  | Non-Toxin |
|     | SSFAAWWTM | 0.7589   | 0.1287       | ALLERGEN      | Non-Toxin |
|     | TTSRSSTSV | 0.7531   | 0.5193       | ALLERGEN      | Non-Toxin |

**Table 2** The decided HTL epitopes for final vaccine building.

| HTL | Epitope          | Percentile Rank | Adjusted Rank | Antigenicity | Allergenicity | Toxicity  |
|-----|------------------|-----------------|---------------|--------------|---------------|-----------|
|     | CTSHMYELSLSSFAA  | 4.40            | 4.40          | 0.4497       | NON-ALLERGEN  | Non-Toxin |
|     | TSHMYELSLSSFAAW  | 4.60            | 4.60          | 0.5164       | NON-ALLERGEN  | Non-Toxin |
|     | AAWWTMLNALILMGA  | 4.90            | 4.90          | 0.2066       | NON-ALLERGEN  | Non-Toxin |
|     | AAWWTMLNALILMGAF | 4.90            | 4.90          | 0.1731       | NON-ALLERGEN  | Non-Toxin |
|     | FAAWWTMLNALILMG  | 4.90            | 4.90          | 0.1351       | ALLERGEN      | Non-Toxin |

**Table 3** The decided LBL epitopes for final vaccine building.

| B cell epitope | Epitope                                  | Start | End | Peptide length | Antigenicity | Allergenicity | Toxicity  |
|----------------|------------------------------------------|-------|-----|----------------|--------------|---------------|-----------|
|                | VAESSGNSSASTSATTSRSTSVSTTK               | 11    | 38  | 28             | 0.5030       | Non ALLERGEN  | Non-Toxin |
|                | TSATTTTTTLSTTSTKLSTTHDPNMRRHANDDFYKAHCTS | 45    | 87  | 43             | 0.5561       | NonALLERGEN   | Non-Toxin |

**Table 4** Physicochemical characteristics of the construct.

| Characteristics                            | Findings                            | Remarks        |
|--------------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|----------------|
| Amino acids                                | 271                                 | suitable       |
| Weight                                     | 28111.58                            | average        |
| Theoretical pI value                       | 6.19                                | Slightly basic |
| Total value of negatively charged residues | 32                                  |                |
| Total value of positively charged residues | 29                                  |                |
| Formula                                    | $C_{1221}H_{1972}N_{328}O_{411}S_9$ |                |
| Total value of atoms                       | 3941                                |                |
| The predicted half-life                    | 30 Hours                            |                |
| The instability index                      | 29.89                               | thermostable   |
| Aliphatic index                            | 70.04                               | stable         |
| Grand average of hydropathicity            | -0.199                              | Hydrophilic    |
| Antigenicity                               | 0.4638                              |                |
| Allergenicity                              | No                                  |                |
| Solubility                                 | 0.620                               |                |

271, the chemical formula was C1221H1972N328O411S9, a total number of atoms: 3941, The volatility index (II) is calculated to be 29.89, aliphatic point was 70.04 and grand average point of hydrophobicity was -0.199(which refers that this vaccine is easily accessible to cell). Physicochemical comments, the immunological control of the construct were estimated. For instance, the antigenicity of the construct was 0.4638 and non-toxin. Again we predicted its solubility (<https://protein-sol.manchester.ac.uk/results/solubility/run-dc634d71e4e905f20faa/results.html>) scale is 0.620 (Figure 3) that meant this is higher soluble, and windowed charge score and fold propensity score are shown in Figures 4,5.



Figure 2 Graphical outline of the expressed multi-epitope vaccine assemble.



Figure 3 Calculated value of solubility using protein sol server.



Figure 4 Windowed charge score per amino acid.

Again, the vaccine was not allergies. The secondary structural figure includes a-helix and arbitrary turns that were assessed using SOPMA site prediction is given in Table 5 and Prispred server prediction are shown in Figure 6.

### Tertiary structure, sophistication and evaluation

“For this we used (<http://galaxy.seoklab.org/index.html>) to generate the highest five models. Among the all models, we decided the model (Figure 7) with the minimum value C-score as recommended by the site.

After refinement step, the vaccine model found 5 (Figure 8) showed that 94.4% residues in the considerable region in the Ramachandran graph, with GDT-HA score 0.9917, RMSD 0.274, MolProbity 2.099, Clash 12.4 and rotamers score 1.4”.

Then we used the Procheck online site (<https://saves.mbi.ucla.edu/>) provided a Table 6 and supplementary file with all findings and ProSA-web server(<https://prosa.services.came.sbg.ac.at/prosa.php>). The total average quality and z score average is -4.55 (Figures 9 & 10).

### Molecular docking investigation

Between them on the Clus Pro v2.0 server provided 29 docked models with different positions. Among these, we took the model with the least energy value (Supplementary file) So, model 1 placed the inclined roles and that was energy score of -1148.6 (supplementary pdf file).

### Molecular dynamics simulation experiment

This was carried out in the iMODS site, where NMA evaluations was submitted to the internal complex. Along with B-factor average, Eigenvalues average, Variance average, Covariance map average, Elastic network average are shown in figure 10A,10B,10C,10D,10E,10F.

### Exempt rejoinder simulation

The safe reply determined comparable to actual immunological aspects produced by special pathogens as confirmed in 11A to 11G. Antigen and immunoglobulins 11A, B lymphocytes cell: these are IgM and IgG2 in 11B, Plasma B lymphocytes count subdivided per isotype (IgM, IgG1 and IgG2) in 11C, CD4 T-helper cells total. Rest values showed in 11C to 11G.

### Codon evolution and in silico cloning

We optimized the codons now in the vaccine create according to the E. coli K12 by the JCat site(<http://jcat.de/>) to develop their key facility. The final constructed size of the vaccine cloning



Figure 5 Windowed fold propensity score per amino acid.



Figure 6 Secondary structure prediction report.

Table 5 The secondary structural features of designated vaccine.

| Features         | Findings      |
|------------------|---------------|
| Alpha helix      | 113 is 41.70% |
| 310 helix        | 0 is 0.00%    |
| Pi helix         | 0 is 0.00%    |
| Beta bridge      | 0 is 0.00%    |
| Extended strand  | 44 is 16.24%  |
| Beta turn        | 0 is 0.00%    |
| Bend region      | 0 is 0.00%    |
| Random coil      | 110 is 40.59% |
| Ambiguous states | 4 is 1.48%    |
| Other states     | 0 is 0.00%    |



Figure 9 Finalisation of the tertiary formation of the vaccine.



Figure 7 Tertiary structure of designated vaccine.



Figure 8 Refined Tertiary structure of designated vaccine.

Table 6 The protein structure and overall structure geometry.

| Features                   | Findings                              |
|----------------------------|---------------------------------------|
| Ramachandran               | 90.4% core 6.3% allow 1.7% gener 1.7% |
| All Ramachandrans averages | 10 labelled residues (out of 263)     |
| Chi1-chi2                  | 0 labelled residues (out of 115)      |
| Side-chain                 | 5 better 0 inside 0 worse             |
| Residue                    | Max.deviation: 17.9 Bad contacts: 0   |
| Bond                       | 6.8 Morris et al class: 1 1 2         |
| G-factors                  | 0.29 Covalent: -0.25 Overall: 0.08    |

product is 5843 bp where the vector was 5363 and insert 480 bp nucleotide base pairs (bp).

## Discussion

Difficulty of CMV disease is the point for developing the vaccine against this viral infection. In this world, CMV is the most prevalent fundamental viral plague [59]. Various examinations



JSmol

**Figure 10** Constructed vaccine after molecular docking.



**Figure 10D** Variance on molecular dynamic simulation.



**Figure 10A** B-factor/Mobility on molecular dynamic simulation.



**Figure 10E** Covariance map on molecular dynamic simulation.



**Figure 10B** B-factor/Mobility on molecular dynamic simulation.



**Figure 10C** Eigenvalues on molecular dynamic simulation.



**Figure 10F** Elastic network on molecular dynamic simulation.



**Figure 11A** Antigen value for immunoglobulin.



**Figure 11D** Total CD4 T-helper lymphocytes count.



**Figure 11B** Total B lymphocytes.



**Figure 11E** Total CD4 T-regulatory lymphocytes count.



**Figure 11C** Total Plasma B lymphocytes.



**Figure 11F** CD8 Total and memory shown.



- cytomegalovirus infection and disease, Multidisciplinary approach to understanding cytomegalovirus disease.
- 11 Ljungman P, Plotkin S (1995) CMV definitions and new syndromes. In: Ehrnst A, Ljungman P (editors). Proceedings from the 5th International Cytomegalovirus Conference (Stockholm). *Scand J Infect Dis* 99: 87-89.
  - 12 Rubin RH (1990) Impact of cytomegalovirus infection on organ transplant recipients. *Rev Infect Dis* 12: S754-766.
  - 13 Grattan MT, Moreno-Cabral CE, Starnes VA, Oyer PE, Stinson EB, et al. (1989) Cytomegalovirus infection is associated with cardiac allograft rejection and atherosclerosis. *JAMA* 261: 3561-3566.
  - 14 Loebe M, Schuler S, Zais O, Warnecke H, Fleck E, et al. (1990) Role of cytomegalovirus infection in the development of coronary artery disease in the transplanted heart. *J Heart Transplant* 9: 707-711.
  - 15 Bando K, Paradis IL, Similo S, Konishi H, Komatsu K, et al. (1995) Obliterative bronchiolitis after lung and heart-lung transplantation: an analysis of risk factors and management. *J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg* 110: 4-13.
  - 16 von Willebrand E, Pettersson E, Ahonen J, Hayry P (1986) CMV infection, class II antigen expression, and human kidney allograft rejection. *Transplantation* 42: 364-367.
  - 17 Fietze E, Prosch S, Reinke P, Stein J, Döcke WD, et al. (1994) Cytomegalovirus infection in transplant recipients: the role of tumor necrosis factor. *Transplantation* 58: 675-680.
  - 18 Reinke P, Fietze E, Ode-Hakim S, Prösch S, Lippert J, et al. (1994) Late-acute renal allograft rejection and symptomless cytomegalovirus infection. *Lancet* 344: 1737-1738.
  - 19 Tollema J, Ringdén O, Boström L, Nilsson B, Sundberg B (1989) Variables predicting deep fungal infection in bone marrow transplant recipients. *Bone Marrow Transplant* 4: 635-641.
  - 20 George MJ, Snyderman DR, Werner BG, Griffith J, Falagas ME, et al. (1997) The independent role of cytomegalovirus as a risk factor for invasive fungal disease in orthotopic liver transplant recipients. Boston Center for Liver Transplantation CMVIG-Study Group. *Am J Med* 103: 106-113.
  - 21 Wagner JA, Ross H, Hunt S, Gamberg P, Valantine H, et al. (1995) Prophylactic ganciclovir treatment reduces fungal as well as cytomegalovirus infections after heart transplantation. *Transplantation* 60: 1473-1477.
  - 22 Lowance D, Neumayer HH, Legendre CM, Squifflet JP, Kovarik J, et al. (1999) Valacyclovir for the prevention of cytomegalovirus disease after renal transplantation. International Valacyclovir Cytomegalovirus Prophylaxis Transplantation Study Group. *N Engl J Med* 340: 1462-1470.
  - 23 Schleiss MR (2008) Cytomegalovirus Vaccine Development. In: Shenk TE, Stinski MF (editors) *Human Cytomegalovirus*. Current Topics in Microbiology and Immunology. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
  - 24 Schleiss MR (2008) Cytomegalovirus Vaccine Development. *Curr Top Microbiol Immunol* 325: 361-382.
  - 25 Elfiky AA (2020) SARS-CoV-2 RNA dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) targeting: An in silico perspective. *J Biomol Struct Dyn* 2020: 1-9.
  - 26 Gaafar BBM, Ali SA, Abd-Elrahman KA, Almofti YA (2019) Immunoinformatics approach for multi-epitope vaccine prediction from H, M, F, and N proteins of Peste des Petits ruminants virus. *Journal of Immunology Research* 2019:6124030.
  - 27 LiW, Joshi MD, Singhanian S, Ramsey KH, Murthy AK, et al. (2014) Peptide vaccine: Progress and challenges. *Vaccines* 2: 515-536.
  - 28 Pickett BE, Sadat EL, Zhang Y, Noronha JM, Squires RB, et al. (2012) ViPR: An open bioinformatics database and analysis resource for virology research. *Nucleic Acids Res* 40: D593-D598.
  - 29 Peng X, Xu X, Li Y, Cheng L, Zhou X, et al. (2020) Transmission routes of 2019-nCoV and controls in dental practice. *International Journal of Oral Science* 12: 9.
  - 30 Doytchinova IA, Flower DR (2007) VaxiJen: A server for prediction of protective antigens, tumour antigens and subunit vaccines. *BMC Bioinformatics* 8: 4.
  - 31 Magnan CN, Zeller M, Kayala MA, Vigil A, Randall A, et al. (2010) High-throughput prediction of protein antigenicity using protein microarray data. *Bioinformatics* 26: 2936-2943.
  - 32 Calis JJA, Maybeno M, Greenbaum JA, Weiskopf D, De Silva AD, et al. (2013) Properties of MHC class I presented peptides that enhance immunogenicity. *PLoS Computational Biology* 9: e1003266.
  - 33 Larsen MV, Lundegaard C, Lamberth K, Buus S, Lund O, et al. (2007) Large-scale validation of methods for cytotoxic T-lymphocyte epitope prediction. *BMC Bioinformatics* 8: 424.
  - 34 Doytchinova IA, Flower DR (2007) VaxiJen: A server for prediction of protective antigens, tumour antigens and subunit vaccines. *BMC Bioinformatics* 8: 4.
  - 35 Gupta S, Kapoor P, Chaudhary K, Gautam A, Kumar R, et al (2013) In silico approach for predicting toxicity of peptides and proteins. *PLoS One* 8: e73957.
  - 36 Dimitrov I, Flower DR, Doytchinova I (2013) AllerTOP – A server for in silico prediction of allergens. *BMC Bioinformatics* 14: S4.
  - 37 Wang P, Sidney J, Kim Y, Sette A, Lund O, et al. (2010). Peptide binding predictions for HLA DR, DP and DQ molecules. *BMC Bioinformatics* 11: 568.
  - 38 Nain Z, Abdulla F, Rahman MM, Karim MM, Khan MSA, et al. (2020) Proteome-wide screening for designing a multi-epitope vaccine against emerging pathogen *Elizabethkingia anophelis* using immunoinformatic approaches. *J Biomol Struct Dyn* 38:4850-4867.
  - 39 Manavalan B, Govindaraj RG, Shin TH, Kim MO, Lee G (2018) iBCE-EL: A new ensemble learning framework for improved linear Bcell epitope prediction. *Front Immunol* 9: 1695.
  - 40 Dorosti H, Eslami M, Negahdaripour M, Ghoshoon MB, Gholami A, et al. (2019) Vaccinomics approach for developing multi-epitope peptide pneumococcal vaccine. *J Biomol Struct Dyn* 37: 3524-3535.
  - 41 Olejnik J, Hume AJ, Muhlberger E (2018) Toll-like receptor 4 in acute viral infection: Too much of a good thing. *PLoS Pathogens* 14: e1007390.
  - 42 Pandey RK, Bhatt TK, Prajapati VK (2018) Novel immunoinformatics approaches to design multi-epitope subunit vaccine for malaria by investigating anopheles salivary protein. *Scientific Reports* 8: 1125.
  - 43 Abdellrazeq GS, Fry LM, Elnaggar MM, Bannantine JP, Schneider DA, et al. (2020) Simultaneous cognate epitope recognition by bovine CD4 and CD8 T cells is essential for primary expansion of antigen-specific cytotoxic T-cells following ex vivo stimulation with

- a candidate *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis* peptide vaccine. *Vaccine* 38: 2016-2025.
- 44 Borthwick N, Silva-Arrieta S, Llano A, Takiguchi M, Brander C, et al. (2020) Novel nested peptide epitopes recognized by CD4<sup>+</sup> T cells induced by HIV-1 conserved-region vaccines. *Vaccines* 8: 28.
  - 45 Gasteiger E, Hoogland C, Gattiker A, Wilkins MR, Appel RD, et al. (2005) Protein identification and analysis tools on the ExPASy server. *The proteomics protocols handbook* pp: 571-607.
  - 46 Geourjon C, Deleage G (1995) SOPMA: Significant improvements in protein secondary structure prediction by consensus prediction from multiple alignments. *Computer Applications in the Biosciences* 11: 681-684.
  - 47 BuchandWA, Minneci F, Nugent TCO, Bryson K, Jones DT (2013) Scalable web services for the PSIPRED Protein Analysis Workbench. *Nucleic Acids Res* 41: W349-W357.
  - 48 Roy A, Kucukural A, Zhang Y (2010) I-TASSER: A unified platform for automated protein structure and function prediction. *Nature Protocols* 5: 725-738.
  - 49 Nugent T, Cozzetto D, Jones DT (2014) Evaluation of predictions in the CASP10 model refinement category. *Proteins* 82: 98-111.
  - 50 DeLano WL (2002) Pymol: An open-source molecular graphics tool. *CCP4 Newsletter on Protein Crystallography*, 40: 82-92.
  - 51 WiedersteinM, SipplM(2007) ProSA-web: Interactive web service for the recognition of errors in three-dimensional structures of proteins. *Nucleic Acids Res* 35: W407-W410.
  - 52 Kozakov D, Hall DR, Xia B, Porter KA, Padhorny D, et al. (2017) The Clus Pro web server for protein-protein docking. *Nature Protocols* 12: 255-278.
  - 53 Sussman JL, Lin D, Jiang J, Manning NO, Prilusky J, et al. (1998) Protein Data Bank (PDB): Database of three-dimensional structural information of biological macromolecules. *Acta Crystallogr D Biol Crystallogr* 54: 1078-1084.
  - 54 Lopez-Blanco JR, Aliaga JI, Quintana-Orti ES, Chacon P (2014) iMODS: Internal coordinates normal mode analysis server. *Nucleic Acids Res* 42: W271-W276.
  - 55 Rapin N, Lund O, Bernaschi M, Castiglione F (2010) Computational immunology meets bioinformatics: The use of prediction tools for molecular binding in the simulation of the immune system. *PLoS One* 5: e9862.
  - 56 Castiglione F, Mantile F, De Berardinis P, Prisco A (2012) How the interval between prime and boost injection affects the immune response in a computational model of the immune system. *Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine* 2012: 842329.
  - 57 Grote A, Hiller K, Scheer M, Munch R, Nortemann B, et al. (2005) JCat: A novel tool to adapt codon usage of a target gene to its potential expression host. *Nucleic Acids Res* 33: W526-W531.
  - 58 Goldberg MF, Roeske EK, Ward LN, Pengo T, Dileepan T, et al. (2018) Salmonella persist in activated macrophages in T cell-sparse granulomas but are contained by surrounding CXCR3 ligand-positioned Th1 cells. *Immunity* 49: 1090-1102.e1097.
  - 59 Whitley RJ (2004) Congenital cytomegalovirus infection: epidemiology and treatment. *Adv Exp Med Biol* 549:155-160.
  - 60 Demmler GJ (1996) Congenital cytomegalovirus infection and disease. *Adv Pediatr Infect Dis* 11:135-162.
  - 61 Colugnati FA, Staras SA, Dollard SC, Cannon MJ (2007) Incidence of cytomegalovirus infection among the general population and pregnant women in the United States. *BMC Infect Dis* 7:71.
  - 62 Pass RF (1996) Immunization strategy for prevention of congenital cytomegalovirus infection. *Infect Agents Dis* 5:240-244.
  - 63 Arvin AM, Fast P, Myers M, Plotkin S, Rabinovich R, et al. (2004) Vaccine development to prevent cytomegalovirus disease: report from the National Vaccine Advisory Committee. *Clin Infect Dis* 39:233-239.
  - 64 Bol KF, Aarntzen EHJG, Pots JM, Olde Nordkamp MAM, van de Rakt, et al. (2016) Prophylactic vaccines are potent activators of monocytederived dendritic cells and drive effective anti-tumor responses in melanoma patients at the cost of toxicity. *Cancer Immunol Immunother* 65: 327-339.
  - 65 Melief CJ, van Hall T, Arens R, Ossendorp F, van der Burg SH (2015) Therapeutic cancer vaccines. *J Clin Invest* 125: 3401-3412.
  - 66 Shamriz S, Ofoghi H, Moazami N (2016) Effect of linker length and residues on the structure and stability of a fusion protein with malaria vaccine application. *Comput Biol Med* 76: 24-29.
  - 67 Bonam SR, Partidos CD, Halmuthur SKM, Muller S(2017) An overview of novel adjuvants designed for improving vaccine efficacy. *Trends Pharmacol Sci* 38: 771-793.
  - 68 Lee S, Nguyen MT (2015) Recent advances of vaccine adjuvants for infectious diseases. *Immune Netw* 15: 51-57.
  - 69 Khatoon N, Pandey RK, Prajapati VK (2017) Exploring Leishmania secretory proteins to design B and T cell multi-epitope subunit vaccine using immunoinformatics approach. *Scientific Reports* 7: 8285.
  - 70 Hossain MI, Islam R, Mimi S, Jewel Z, Haider U(2020)Gut Microbiota Gut Microbiota: Succinct Overview of Impacts on Human Physique and Current Research Status with Future Aspects. *Int J Adv Life Sci Research* 3: 1-10.